

Quarterly International Journal

ISSN No. 2320 - 7892

INDO GLOBAL JOURNAL OF APPLIED MANAGEMENT SCIENCE

Volume: 3

Issue : 2

September 2015

Promoted by :

**The Kongu Regional Educational
and Research Foundation**
Salem, Tamil Nadu.

	Title of the paper	Page No
12	ASSESSING THE EFFECTS OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT (HRM) PRACTICES ON EMPLOYEE JOB PERFORMANCE <i>P. Dhanalakshmi, Dr. S. Sasikumar,</i>	43
13	A STUDY ON ISLAMIC BANKING <i>J. Asanya Fathima</i>	49
14	THE CURRENT STATE OF COUNSELLING RESEARCH AND PRACTICE: CONCERNS, DIRECTIONS, AND IMPLICATIONS FOLLOWED IN TOP NOTCH FIRMS <i>K.R. Kishore Kumar, Dr. Muthu Natarajan,</i>	51
15	A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF WOMEN EMPOWERMENT IN SELECTED NGOS OF BUNDELKHAND AREA <i>Dr. A. K. Malviya, Manu Shukla,</i>	56
16	STRESS MANAGEMENT AMONG WOMEN LECTURERS IN THE SELF - FINANCING COLLEGES IN CHENNAI CITY. <i>N. Maheswari</i>	61
17	VALUE CREATION AND BUSINESS STRATEGIES IN E-AGE <i>J. Jasmine Selvapackiam</i>	66
18	ASSESSING PRACTICES OF LEADERSHIP IN THE CASE OF CONSTRUCTION AND BUSINESBANK S.C (CBB) <i>G/Medhin W/Yohannes</i>	68
19	A STUDY OF IMPACT OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE ON TEAMWORK <i>Dr. Jyoti Sharma</i>	73
20	IMPACT OF COMMUNICATION AND FEEDBACK ON EMPLOYEE PARTICIPATION <i>Dr. Jyoti Sharma</i>	78
21	HEALTH STATUS OF INDIAN WOMEN: A STUDY <i>Sarika Dixit</i>	81
22	THE IMPACT OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY ON YOUTH <i>Dr. Varsha Patel</i>	84
23	A STUDY OF WORK RELATED STRESS FACTORS AFFECTING WORK LIFE BALANCE IN SERVICE SECTOR ESPECIALLY IN PALLAVA GRAMA BANK VILLUPURAM <i>D. Shoba, Dr. G. Suganthi</i>	88

A STUDY OF WORK RELATED STRESS FACTORS AFFECTING WORK LIFE BALANCE IN SERVICE SECTOR ESPECIALLY IN PALLAVA GRAMA BANK VILLUPURAM

D. SHOBA, Asst. Prof,

Theivanai Ammal College for Women, Villupuram

Dr. G. SUGANTHI, Head and Asst. Prof,

Government Arts College, C Mutlur, chidambaram

ABSTRACT

Work related stress factors play a major role in the work life balance irrespective of the personal stress factors, organizational setups and other factors. The work life stressors of every individual affect the Work-life harmony and work efficiency. In this study an attempt is made to study about the work related stressors which affect more on the work life harmony in and ultimately results in work life imbalance. The sample is collected from 450 employees. The expert's linguistic opinions are analyzed using ANOVA to find out the work related stressor which is the major reason for work life imbalance and affects the work life harmony. Findings provide valuable managerial information to guide suitable strategies enhancing the work-life balance experience and by implication employees' general wellbeing, job satisfaction and commitment. This study contributes to the evolving body of knowledge with regard to work-life balance and provides a unique context-specific perspective to the conceptual understanding of the construct.

Keywords: Stress, Work related Stressors, Work Life balance,

Introduction

Work Life Balance

Work life balance is about people having measure of their control over when, where and how they work. Most of the people view the work life balance is what the organization allows for an individual to experience. However, work-life balance is a bi-dimensional approach. The other dimension of work-life balance, which many individuals overlook, relates to what individuals do for themselves. The success of work life balance is always sustained with achievement along with enjoyment. Achievement and enjoyment at work is a critical part of work-life balance. Moreover, achievement and enjoyment in the other three quadrants of one's life (e.g. family, friends and self) is critical as well. Stress occurs in many different circumstances, but is particularly strong when a person's ability to control the demands of work is threatened. The importance of the balance between personal life and work life is ignored today. The imbalance also has a negative impact in the personal life of working people, some of which have even become social hazards increasing number of divorces, infertility due to high stress levels, nuclear families etc.

Stress

Stress is a natural factor that acts from inside or outside of the world and influencing the individual. Every response to stress will affect the particular individual as well as the environment. As we experience the high stress in day today life, we often perceive it as a negative experience; however, the stress can also be experienced as positive to some extent. In general, stress is related to both external and internal factors.

External factors include the physical environment, including job, relationships with others, challenges, difficulties and expectations deal with on a daily basis. Internal factors decide the way to respond and deal with the external stressors. Internal factors which influence the ability to handle stress include nutritional status, overall health and fitness levels, emotional well-being and the amount of sleep and rest one gets.

Work related stressors which affect the work life balance:

Stress can strike anyone at any level of the business and recent research (4) shows that work related stress is prevalent and is not restricted to particular sectors, jobs or industries. Job stress is a persistent illness caused by conditions in the workplace that negatively affect an individual's performance and/or overall well-being of his body and mind. One or more physical and mental illnesses manifests job stress. In some cases, job stress can be disabling. In chronic cases a psychiatric consultation is usually required to validate the reason and degree of work related stress. In the early stages job stress can boost the body and enhance performance in the workplace, thus the term 'I perform better under pressure'. However, if this condition is allowed to go continuously and the body is depleted further, the performance ultimately declines and the person's health degenerates. Due to these health issues and the anxiety caused by the stress at work effectively influence the work life balance. The subject individual is unable to manage work and life and thus fail in either of these or both of these. In this study, the expert's opinion used to determine which work related stressor have more influence in destroying the work life harmony and lead to work life imbalance.

Stresses at Work

The demands of modern lifestyle and modern organizational setups are inducing stress and acting as a stress factors. Stress at work is not affecting the individual but also affects the organization. Work related stress starts when one cannot cope up with the modern day's deadlines and long working hours. Stress is a well-known and very common trouble in today's workplace. As per Princeton Survey Research Associates Labor Day survey states, about one-third of workers report high levels of stress. One-quarter of employees sight their jobs as the number one stressor in their lives. Three-quarters of employees suppose the worker has more on-the-job stress than a generation ago [10].

As per Michael Kahn, Work-related stress study finds evidence suggests that stress is the major cause of revenue in organizations. With chronic stress at the workplace, workers will build up psychological and physiological dysfunctions and decreased motivation in excelling in their position [4]. The Lenexa Research Institute released a global survey of almost 30,000 workers which showed that females suffered more workplace stress than their male counterparts [17].

According to the survey, women's stress level were 10% higher for those in supervisory positions, 8% higher stress in service and production jobs than men, and 6% higher in middle and upper management than men in the same position. Professional stress or job stresses always have a threat to physical health. Work related stress in the life of organized workers, consequently, affects the health of organizations. Work-related stress can be caused by various factors. For example, a person might feel under pressure if the demands of their job (such as hours or responsibilities) are greater than they can comfortably manage. Other sources of work-related stress include conflict with coworkers or bosses, work harassment and threats to job security. What one person may perceive as stressful, however, another may view as challenging.

Stressor

A stressor is anything that causes the release of stress hormones. There are two broad categories of stressors: Physiological (or physical) stressors and Psychological Stressors.

Physiological (or physical) stressors: These are stressors that put strain on our body (i.e., very cold/hot temperatures, injury, chronic illness or pain).

Psychological Stressors: These are events, situations, individuals, comments or anything we interpret as negative or threatening (i.e., love failure, death, fired from job, etc).

Adaptation of the problem:

There are many factors contributing to work related stress and all the stress inducing factors (stressors) will lead to work life imbalance. It is known that all the stressors affect the work life balance in some degree. Eleven stress inducing factors are derived from expert's opinion and to find out which stressor has more influence in provoking the other stress inducing factors and result in work life imbalance. With the help of expert's opinion the data has been arrived

- A1 - Excessive work load
- A2 - Unimportant and meaningless tasks
- A3 - Conflicting job demands
- A4 - Distant or unreachable supervisors
- A5 - Multiple supervisors
- A6 - Lack of individual autonomy and co-operation in decision making
- A7 - Poor performance from co-workers
- A8 - Conflicts and competition among staff
- A9 - Workplace bullying or harassment
- A10 - Long working time
- A11 - Low payment

IV. OVERALL STRESS EFFECT:

S.NO		Teaching	
		Frequency	%age
A1	Excessive work load	21	45.50
A2	Unimportant and meaningless tasks	2	03.33
A3	Conflicting job demands	5	11.11
A4	Distant or unreachable supervisors	8	16.66
A5	Multiple supervisors	5	09.77
A6	Lack of individual autonomy and co -operation in decision making	0	00.00
A7	Poor performance from co-workers	4	08.66
A8	Conflict and competition among workers	0	00.00
A9	Workplace bullying or harassment	0	00.00
A10	Long working time	0	00.00
A11.	Low payment	45	100.0

Stresses at Work

The demands of modern lifestyle and modern organizational setups are inducing stress and acting as a stress factors. Stress at work is not affecting the individual but also affects the organization. Work related stress starts when one cannot cope up with the modern day's deadlines and long working hours. Stress is a well-known and very common trouble in today's workplace. As per Princeton Survey Research Associates Labor Day survey states, about one-third of workers report high levels of stress. One-quarter of employees sight their jobs as the number one stressor in their lives. Three-quarters of employees suppose the worker has more on-the-job stress than a generation ago [10].

As per Michael Kahn, Work-related stress study finds evidence suggests that stress is the major cause of revenue in organizations. With chronic stress at the workplace, workers will build up psychological and physiological dysfunctions and decreased motivation in excelling in their position [4]. The Lenexa Research Institute released a global survey of almost 30,000 workers which showed that females suffered more workplace stress than their male counterparts [17].

According to the survey, women's stress level were 10% higher for those in supervisory positions, 8% higher stress in service and production jobs than men, and 6% higher in middle and upper management than men in the same position. Professional stress or job stresses always have a threat to physical health. Work related stress in the life of organized workers, consequently, affects the health of organizations. Work-related stress can be caused by various factors. For example, a person might feel under pressure if the demands of their job (such as hours or responsibilities) are greater than they can comfortably manage. Other sources of work-related stress include conflict with coworkers or bosses, work harassment and threats to job security. What one person may perceive as stressful, however, another may view as challenging.

Stressor

A stressor is anything that causes the release of stress hormones. There are two broad categories of stressors: Physiological (or physical) stressors and Psychological Stressors.

Physiological (or physical) stressors: These are stressors that put strain on our body (i.e., very cold/hot temperatures, injury, chronic illness or pain).

Psychological Stressors: These are events, situations, individuals, comments or anything we interpret as negative or threatening (i.e., love failure, death, fired from job, etc).

Adaptation of the problem:

There are many factors contributing to work related stress and all the stress inducing factors (stressors) will lead to work life imbalance. It is known that all the stressors affect the work life balance in some degree. Eleven stress inducing factors are derived from expert's opinion and to find out which stressor has more influence in provoking the other stress inducing factors and result in work life imbalance. With the help of expert's opinion the data has been arrived

- A1 - Excessive work load
- A2 - Unimportant and meaningless tasks
- A3 - Conflicting job demands
- A4 - Distant or unreachable supervisors
- A5 - Multiple supervisors
- A6 - Lack of individual autonomy and co-operation in decision making
- A7 - Poor performance from co-workers
- A8 - Conflicts and competition among staff
- A9 - Workplace bullying or harassment
- A10 - Long working time
- A11 - Low payment

IV. OVERALL STRESS EFFECT:

S.NO		Teaching	
		Frequency	%age
A1	Excessive work load	21	45.50
A2	Unimportant and meaningless tasks	2	03.33
A3	Conflicting job demands	5	11.11
A4	Distant or unreachable supervisors	8	16.66
A5	Multiple supervisors	5	09.77
A6	Lack of individual autonomy and co -operation in decision making	0	00.00
A7	Poor performance from co-workers	4	08.66
A8	Conflict and competition among workers	0	00.00
A9	Workplace bullying or harassment	0	00.00
A10	Long working time	0	00.00
A11.	Low payment	45	100.0

ANOVA TABLE

	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean square	F
Between columns	809.25	3	MSC=269.75	MSC/MSE=5.93
Between rows	469.25	3	MSR=156.41	MSR/MSE=3.43
Residual or Error	409.25	9	MSE=45.47	
Total sum of squares	1687.75	15		

Results and discussions:

The result of the study indicates that the on state of the attribute distant and unreachable supervisors (A4) leads to the on state of the attributes excessive work load (A1), conflicting job demands (A3), lack of individual autonomy and co-operation in decision making (A6), poor performance from co-workers (A7) and long working time (A10).

Conclusion:

It is evident that when the supervisor is in distant or unreachable there would be no control over the employees and employees have no place to show their dissatisfaction or negative stress about the job. Since the supervisor is unreachable the excessive work load stressor cannot be reported to the supervisor and hence the employee would feel helpless which itself is a stressor. Conflicting job demands cannot be clarified with the supervisor as the supervisor is in distant or unreachable. Again, since the supervisor is unreachable, individual autonomy in decision making is affected due to the fact that the supervisor is not there to back the employee, this results in poor performance. Long working hours also left unreported to their supervisor for any resolution. Thus distant or unreachable supervisor is major stressor which ultimately resulted in many other work related stressors and thus the work life harmony gets affected.

Future direction:

This paper dealt with the work related stressors which comes under the broad area of psychological stressors, however the study can be further extended into personal stressors such as family issue, health issue, financial problems, etc. Also, the study can be industry specific that is, the study can be done in a particular industries like medical, pharmacy, BPO, IT, Govt. Sector, Banks, etc and find the stress inducing factors which affects the work life harmony. Moreover, the study can be extended to find which gender is more vulnerable to stress and thus get affected by the work life imbalance.

References:

- [1] Adrew Baum, Richard J Contrada, "the hand book stress science- biology, psychology and health" (2010).
- [2] Clifford Morgan, Richard King, John Weisz, Schopler, "Introduction To Psychology" Mcgraw- Hill Education (India) Pvt Limited, (2001).
- [3] Fiona Jones, Ronald Burke And Mina Westman, "Work Life Balance: A Psychological Perspective". Psychology Press (Uk), (2006).
- [4] Michael Kahn, Work-Related Stress Can Kill, Study Finds: [Http://Www.Reuters.Com/ Article/2008/01/23/Usheart-Stress-Idusl2284632220080123](http://www.Reuters.Com/Article/2008/01/23/Usheart-Stress-Idusl2284632220080123).(2008)
- [5] Mohammad Niaz Asadullah And Rosa M. Fernández "Work-Life Balance Practices And The Gender Gap In Job Satisfaction In The Uk: Evidence From Matched Employer-Employee Data"(2008).
- [6] Morgan And King C.T, "Introduction To Psychology" Tata Mcgraw-Hill Education (2001).
- [7] Niharika Doble And Supriya, M.V, "Gender Differences In The Perception Of Work Life Balance".(2010)
- [8] Stress At Work. U.S. National Institute For Occupational Safety And Health, Dhhs (Niosh) Publication Number 99-101. (1999)
- [9] Occupational Stress: [Http://En.Wikipedia.Org/Wiki/Occupational_Stress](http://En.Wikipedia.Org/Wiki/Occupational_Stress)
- [10] Princeton Survey Research Associates Labor Data Survey: State Of Workers. Princeton, Nj: Princeton Survey Research Associates (1997).
- [11] robert karasek, tores theorell "healthy work: stress, productivity, and the reconstruction of working life" (1992).
- [12] Stress at work: <http://www.lifepositive.com/main/psychology/stress/stress-at-work.asp>.